

Comparative study on the geographical, physical and engineering properties of soils of West Bengal. Part-II : Field test (experimental methods) working equations and engineering properties of soils of North Bengal

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Abstract : The experimental methods for the determination of mechanical properties of soils based on field tests, the basic equations for the determination of the design values of the bearing capacity according to the load of the superstructure and the properties of the sub soils have been described. The mechanical (engineering) properties of soil samples of North Bengal have also been described.

Keywords : Bearing capacity, consolidation test, dynamic cone penetration test, foundation, North Bengal, soils, static cone penetration test.

Introduction

In Part-I of this paper¹, studies on the geographical aspects of West Bengal like land elevation, slope of the rivers, some physical and engineering properties of soils like grain size of the river sands, free-swell index and permeability of soils of different parts of West Bengal were determined and useful conclusions were derived.

But for construction purposes (for the construction of roads, bridges, dams, buildings etc.) knowledge of different physical and engineering properties of soils is needed. In a recent communication², some of these properties like moisture content, specific gravity, dry density, void ratio, porosity, degree of saturation, Attenberg limits (liquid limit, plastic limit), plasticity ratio etc. for soils of deltaic regions of West Bengal have been described. Some physico-chemical and agronomic aspects of soils in the deltaic region were also reported³. However, most of the properties are laboratory based. The determination of other soil mechanical properties based on field tests like standard penetration test (SPT), static cone penetration test (SCPT), dynamic cone penetration test (DCPT), plate load test (PLT), compaction test, shear

test, consolidation test etc. are necessary to understand the soil properties for the purpose of design of different structures mentioned before.

The object of the present communication is to describe the different field test for the determination of mechanical properties of soils, the basic equations necessary to derive design values of bearing capacity according to the load of the superstructure and the properties of the sub soils.

The results of our investigation on the mechanical (engineering) properties of soils of North Bengal are also presented in this paper.

Experimental

The method of collection of undisturbed soil samples for laboratory test was described in Part-I¹ of the paper. In the present experiment soils samples were not collected. The strength, consistency and other properties like SPT, SCPT, DCPT etc. were determined in the proper sites. In these sites, collection of soils samples is difficult due to sand and soil below the ground water tables.

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Field testing⁴⁻¹⁴ :

(i) *Standard penetration test (SPT) :*

The test is done within a bored hole. A thick-walled split tube sampler of 50 mm outer diameter, 35 mm inner diameter and 60 cm or more length is driven under the blows of a 65 kg drive weight with 75 cm free fall. The penetration resistance is the number of blows (N_s) (i.e. blow count) required to drive the sampler through 30 cm. N_s is higher in a dense sand and in a stiff clay compared to a loose sand and soft clay. The Charts/Tables 1 and 2 for N_s vs shear parameters may be used to get the required parameters for design purposes.

(ii) *Static cone penetration test (SCPT) or Dutch cone penetration test :*

It gives a continuous record of the resistance of soil obtained by penetrating steadily a cone of base area 10 cm² and apex angle 60° at the vertex. The cone with jacket is connected with hollow mantle tubes having a rod within each tube. The arrangement is such that when pushed from top, the resistance experienced by the cone is transferred through the rod to the oil chamber of the apparatus having two hydraulic gauges. More the resistance, more is the reading in the gauges.

The cone penetration resistance is utilised to get the allowable bearing capacity directly or to get the shear parameters of the soils. At each depth (at an interval of 20 cm, generally) cone and cone plus jacket friction readings are obtained. Frictional resistance is obtained by deducting reading one from reading two. Friction value is utilised in estimating frictional resistance of a pile foundation.

Correlation of the blow count (N_s), cone penetration resistance (C_{kd}) and angle of internal friction (ϕ) of sands are obtained from the standard tables (Tables 1 and 2). Similar correlations are available between cone penetration resistance and cohesion of clays. In the present investigation, results using a manually driven penetrometer (N.V. Goudsche Machine fabriek-Gouda, 2t) have been presented. This Dutch apparatus has a unique facility. A sampler unit with a cutter (mouth locked initially) of inner diameter 32.5 mm and length 200 mm can be attached to a hollow mantle tube. It may be pushed to the desired depth, unlocked and pushed further to collect the soil in the cutter. It is then sheared and lifted up.

(iii) *Dynamic cone penetration test :*

In this test a cone of diameter 50–65 mm with apex angle 60° is used. In contrast to SPT no boring is required prior to this test, and it gives a continuous record

of the blow count (no. of blows/30 cm). Denser the sand is or stiffer the clay is, higher is the blow count, conversely in loose sand and soft clay, blow count is less. The SPT tables for " N_s vs ϕ " etc. may also be used with this test data with necessary corrections.

(iv) *Compaction test :*

Sand is made dense by vibration and clay is made dense by compaction or by consolidation under load. When a clayey soil is used as a construction material e.g. in the construction of an earthen embankment to be used as a dam, highway, railway etc., loose soil is made dense by the rollers. The target density and moisture are usually obtained by conducting standard proctor compaction test in the laboratory.

By compaction of a soil in a dense state, its shear strength is increased, settlement tendency is reduced and permeability is also reduced. When water is added to a soil, the particles adsorb water and force is applied, air gets expelled out to some extent as the particles slide over each other due to lubrication by water. The result is the increased density of the soil mass. Further addition of water leads to more lubrication and more density under load applied by impact. But beyond optimum amount of water, further addition of water does not help in reducing void, as air permeability gets highly reduced. More water makes more void volume, net result being decrease in density. The peak point in the dry density versus moisture content plot gives the maximum dry density and optimum moisture content.

The main mould has a height of 11.7 cm, diameter 10.15 cm and volume 945 c.c. There is one extension collar. Moist soil is put in the mould and a rammer of 2.5 kg (5.5 lb) is allowed to fall freely from a height 30.5 cm (12"). 25 blows are given on the soil layer. The mould with extension collar is filled with three of such layers. Extension piece is removed and the main mould is dressed. Weight of the soil in the mould is taken. Water is added further and the test is done once more. For each density, corresponding moisture content is taken. Thus six to seven points of different dry density and moisture content values are obtained. A dry density versus moisture content curve is obtained, from which the maximum dry density and the corresponding optimum value of moisture content are obtained. At the optimum stage the degree of saturation is obtained in the range of 65–80% (generally).

(v) *Shear test :*

When soil mass is loaded, shearing stresses is induced

in it. The shear strength of a soil is the resistance to deformation by continuous shear displacement of soil particles upon the action of shear stress. The shearing resistance of a soil is constituted basically of the following components :

- (i) The resistance due to interlocking of the particles,
- (ii) The frictional resistance at the contact points of individual soil particles and
- (iii) Cohesion or adhesion between the surfaces of the soil particles.

The theory of failure of a soil mass under load can be expressed algebraically by the equation $s = C + \sigma \tan \phi$ where s is the shear resistance of the soil, σ is the normal stress and C, ϕ are empirical constants. C is usually termed as cohesion and ϕ is the angle of internal friction or shearing resistance. These are also called shear strength parameters. C is usually zero or nearly zero in sandy soils and ϕ is zero or nearly zero in saturated clayey soils. But $C - \phi$ are obtained in intermediate soils or unsaturated clayey soils. There are three types of shear test viz. unconfined compression test, direct shear test and triaxial test. The first one is done on saturated clays ($\phi = 0$) but the other types of test can be done on any type of soil.

In a shear test, a soil specimen is usually made to undergo deformation at a constant rate and resistance is noted (strain controlled test procedure). This is continued till the specimen fails i.e. reaches its maximum resistance value. In direct shear test a specimen of size 6 cm × 6 cm × 2.5 cm is used and in triaxial and unconfined compression tests 3.8 cm diameter and 7.6 cm long cylindrical specimens are used. When failure point is reached, clean lines of failure at or near 45° appear or the sample fails by bulging without showing clear failure lines.

In direct shear test three or more specimens are tested at different normal stress values. The shear stress versus normal stress plot is used to get shear parameters. Triaxial tests may be done by imposing drained and undrained conditions in order to simulate the actual conditions that the soil may experience in field. Before the test the specimen is covered with latex membrane, placed within the cell, the cell is filled with water and test is done under a cell pressure. Results of the tests under different cell pressures are utilized to develop different Mohr circles and the shear parameters are obtained. Failure load divided by the corrected area gives the failure stress and half the failure stress gives the cohesion or undrained shear strength of the soil. Some times the strain corresponding to 1/2 or

1/3 the failure stress is used to get stress-strain ratio. This value designated as E gives the secant modulus or Young's modulus of that clayey soil.

The values of the shear parameters obtained in any of the tests are utilized in evaluating the bearing capacity of a foundation structure on the soil. For cohesive soils Skempton's¹³ equation may be used and for any type of soil Terzaghi's¹¹ equation and bearing capacity parameters corresponding to the shear parameters may be utilized.

(vi) *Consolidation test :*

When a saturated soil mass is subjected to a load increment, it is carried initially by water as it is incompressible compared to soil structure. This pressure is termed as hydrostatic excess pressure. But gradually water comes out, the volume of the soil mass is reduced and the load is ultimately carried by the soil grains. The volume of water drained out is equal to the volume change in the soil mass. The process is known as consolidation.

In sands immediate settlement due to elastic distortions mainly occur under imposed load. Consolidation phenomenon is associated with clays mainly. In nature, soil sediments consolidate and become stable under self-weight.

The main purpose of a consolidation test in laboratory is to obtain soil parameters that are used in predicting the rate of settlement of a structure founded on a clay. The two most important soil properties are (i) the compression index, C_c , that indicates the magnitude of the rate of settlement with increasing load on the soil specimen and (ii) the co-efficient, C_v , that indicates the time rate of settlement under a load increment.

As the consolidation data of a small soil specimen in utilised in predicting the settlement of a natural soil stratum under a structure, the results are expressed in a normalised form, void ratio (e) against load intensity (p) in a semi-log plot, popularly known as $e - \log p$ plot. The slope of the $e - \log p$ plot is given as C_c , the compression index. Generally, softer the soil is and higher the LL^2 is, more is the value of C_c . The actual settlement of a structure in field is given by the Terzaghi's equation,

$$s = H \frac{C_c}{1 + e_0} \log \frac{p_0 + \Delta p}{p_0}$$

where, s = settle of the soil mass in actual field, C_c = compression index, e_0 = initial void ratio, p_0 = initial vertical stress intensity, Δp = super imposed load of the structure and H = thickness of clay layer undergoing

consolidation i.e. the depth which is effected by the load increment.

In nature, clay may be normally consolidated or over consolidated. When the present load (p_0) is equal to the maximum load (p_c) the soil stratum has experienced since its origin, the clayey soil is termed as normally consolidated clay (NC). If the present load is less than the maximum load the soil has experienced in the geological past, it is termed as an over consolidated clay (OC). An NC clay is of soft to medium consistency and its natural moisture content is nearer to LL than to PL². On the contrary an OC clay may be medium, stiff or very stiff and its moisture content may be near to PL and even lower than PL. In an NC clay one value of C_c is obtained. But in an OC clay two values are obtained, one for over-consolidated range [for ($p_0 + \Delta p$) < p_c] and the other for the normally consolidated range.

Usually the consolidation soil mould has a diameter to thickness ratio of 3 to 4. In the experiments presented in the paper. AIMIL make 3 gang fixed ring consolidometer was used ($D = 60$ mm, $H = 20$ mm, $D/H = 3$). Silicon grease was smeared inside the brass mould to minimize wall friction. 24 h time was allowed for dissipation of pore pressure under each load increment and the load

intensities used were 0.2, 0.4, 0.8, 1.6, 3.2, 6.4 kg/cm². The load was applied through a lever system and the change in the dial reading due to load increment was noticed. The difference of initial and the final readings (after 24 h) gave the settlement under that load increment. From the data the void ratio under a load was evaluated. Thus for different load intensities different e values were obtained and a $e - \log p$ curve was obtained for the soil.

(vii) *Sedimentation in laboratory :*

The method was described in the previous communications^{15,16}.

In order to make our observations comprehensive the data for other tests were utilized from the data available in the technical publication of the River Research Institute¹⁷.

Results

Based on the experimental results, the different equations and tables given below are utilised to understand the nature of the soils from the mechanical point of view. The correlation of the blow count (N_s), cone penetration resistance (C_{kd}) and angle of internal friction (ϕ) of sand are obtained from the standard Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. Values of safe bearing capacity according to Indian Standard IS : 1904-1961

Sl. no.	Description of soil capacity	Safe bearing capacity (t/m ²), (1 kg/cm ² = 10 t/m ²)
(A) Cohesionless soils :		
1.	Gravel, sand and gravel, compact and offering high resistance to penetration when excavated by tools	45
2.	Coarse sand, compact and dry	45
3.	Medium sand, compact and dry	25
4.	Fine sand, silt (dry lumps easily pulverized by fingers)	15
5.	Loose gravel or sand gravel mixture, loose coarse to medium sand, dry	25
6.	Find sand, loose and dry	10
(B) Cohesive soils :		
1.	Soft shale, hard or stiff clay in deep bed, dry	45
2.	Medium clay readily indented with a thumb nail	25
3.	Moist clay and sand clay mixture which can be indented with a strong thumb pressure	15
4.	Soft clay indented with moderate thumb pressure	10
5.	Very soft clay which can be penetrated by several inches with the thumb	5
6.	Black cotton soil or other shrinkable or expansive clay in dry condition (50% saturation)	15

Table 2. Some relations between cone resistance, blow count and different parameters for engineering uses

(A) Relationship between C_{kd} and ABC :

C_{kd} = Cone penetration resistance, kg/cm²
 or, total ultimate bearing capacity of cone which is a circular footing of base area 10 cm²
 ABC = Total allowable bearing capacity of strip footing with a factor of safety = 4

$$ABC = \frac{C_{kd}}{10} \text{ kg/cm}^2 [1 \text{ kg/cm}^2 = 10 \text{ t/m}^2]$$

(B) Relationship between N_s and C_{kd} [Schmertmann, 1970] :

N_s = Blow count (no. of blows/30 cm penetration) in standard penetration test
 C_{kd} = Cone penetration resistance, kg/cm² in static cone penetration test

Sl. no.	Description of soil	C_{kd}/N_s (kg/cm ²)
1.	Slits, sandy slits, slightly cohesive silt-sand mixtures	2.0
2.	Clean fine to medium sands and silty	3.5
3.	Coarse sands and sands with little gravel	5.0
4.	Sandy gravel and gravel	6.0

(C) Relationship between N_s and N :

N_s = Blow count in standard penetration test
 N = Blow count in dynamic cone penetration test
 $N = C.N_s$

If diameter of cone is 65 mm and bentonite slurry is used during penetration, $C = 0.8$ to 1.2

(D) Empirical relation between N_s and ϕ of cohesionless soils :

N_s	ϕ , degree	Relative density (D_r)	Description	Approximate, moist density (g/c.c.)
0-4	25-30	0-15	Very loose	1.12-1.60
4-10	27-32	15-35	Loose	1.14-1.84
10-30	30-35	35-65	Medium	1.76-2.08
30-50	35-40	65-85	Dense	1.76-2.24
> 50	38-43	85-100	Very dense	2.08-2.40

(E) Empirical relation between N_s and C_u of cohesive soils :

N_s	C_u (t/m ²)	Saturated density (g/c.c.)	Consistency
0	0	1.6-1.92	Very soft
2	1.25		Soft
4	2.5	1.76-2.08	Medium
8	5.0		Stiff
16	10.0	1.92-2.24	Very stiff
32	20.0		Hard

Similar correlation are available between cone penetration resistance and cohesion of clays (Tables 1 and 2).

Bearing capacity equations :

(i) Terzaghi's general bearing capacity equation¹¹ :

$$q_{ultn} = CN_c + \gamma DN_q + 0.5 \gamma BN\gamma \quad (1)$$

D = Foundation depth, B = width of foundation, γ = soil density, C = cohesion, q_{ultn} = net ultimate bearing capacity i.e. ultimate bearing capacity minus stress due to self weight of soil and N_c , N_q , $N\gamma$ = bearing capacity factors due to cohesion, surcharge and weight of sub soil below foundation respectively.

(ii) Skempton's¹³ recommendation of evaluating bearing capacity of purely cohesive soils ($\phi = 0$) :

$$q_{ultn} = C_u \cdot N_c (1 + 0.2 B/L) (1 + 0.2 D/B)$$

where $N_c = 5$ (2)

B = Width of footing, L = length of footing, D = depth of footing, N_c = bearing capacity parameter and C_u = undrained shear strength or cohesion.

Suitable factor of safety (generally, 3) may be applied on net q_{ultn} to get net safe bearing capacity for design purposes.

Discussion

Before discussion of the soil properties it is desirable to have some idea about foundations and design value of the bearing capacity of soils.

Foundations and design value of bearing capacity of soils :

A foundation placed on a soil should be such that it bears the superimposed load safely and does not settle more than some specified limits. The foundation or

substructure is chosen according to the load of the superstructure and the properties of the sub soils. Ground improvement technique like soil stabilization are followed to change the soil properties so that the sub soils become fit to bear the designed load within short time. A list of safe bearing capacity of different types of soils in the Indian code of practice is available (Tables 1 and 2). For safe and economic foundation design and construction, the results of different field and laboratory tests may be utilised. The ultimate bearing capacity is divided by suitable value of factor of safety (usually 2.5 to 4) to get allowable or safe bearing capacity. This value may further be checked against suitable settlement criteria to arrive at the safe design value.

The results of field tests and laboratory tests (mechanical analysis, cone penetration tests, Atterberg limits etc.) of soils of North Bengal (Geographical regions 1-4) are given in Table 3. Two typical Figs. (1 and 2) showing the variation of the bearing capacities (Table 2) of soils with explanation are given.

Fig. 1. Soil profile at Lichupakuri, Darjeeling (Region-2).

Table 3. Index properties of the soil samples collected from different sites of West Bengal

Sample no.	Site	Geographical region	Reduced level (m)	Figure no. 4	Depth below ground level (m)	Particle size distribution			Atterberg limit's LL	United soil classification	Dry density (g/c.c.)	Moisture content (%)	Shear parameters			
						Gravel (>0.06 mm)	Silt (0.06-0.002 mm)	Clay (<0.002 mm)					C _u (kg/cm ²)	φ	K (cm/s)	C _c
A-1	Lichupakuri, Darjeeling	2	101.4	-	1.9-2.1	78.0	22.0	-	Non-plastic	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A-2	do	do	-	-	2.8-3.0	94.5	5.5	-	do	1.41	15	-	0.05	32°	7.3 × 10 ⁻³	-
A-3	do	do	-	-	3.7-4.0	5.0	77.7	17.3	do	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A-4	do	6	-	4A	4.0-4.2	8.5	77.0	14.5	do	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A-5	do	do	-	-	4.6-4.9	61.0	34.2	4.8	do	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A-6	do	do	-	-	5.5-5.9	84.5	14.3	1.2	do	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
B-1	Baurigachh, Dinajpur (N)	3	70.7	-	1.2-1.5	100.0	-	-	Non-plastic	1.44	18	-	-	30.5°	2.2 × 10 ⁻²	-
B-2	do	do	-	4B	2.6-2.9	100.0	-	-	do	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
B-3	do	do	-	-	3.8-4.0	100.0	-	-	do	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
C-1	Islampur, Dinajpur (N)	3	56.5	4C	2.0-2.2	45.0	42.1	12.9	Non-plastic	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
C-2	do	do	-	-	3.5-3.7	96.7	3.3	-	do	-	-	-	-	-	5 × 10 ⁻⁷	0.46
D-1	Panchanandapur, Malda	3	20.9	-	1.9-2.2	8	71.1	20.9	40	25	38	0.4	CI	1.25	-	-
D-2	do	do	-	4D	3.4-3.6	-	-	-	46	24	50.8	0.27	CI	1.15	-	-
D-3	do	do	-	-	4.0-4.2	-	-	-	61	30	52	0.31	CH	1.28	-	-
D-4	do	do	-	-	6.0-6.2	93.8	6.2	-	Non-plastic	-	16	-	-	1.51	-	34°

Fall-cum-cart bridge site – Dauk Nagar main canal

Fig. 2. Soil profile at the site near Islampur, Dinajpur (N) (Region-3).

Fig. 1 : The sub soils in the upper 2 m are mainly sandy whitish in color with medium capacity values from 2 to 5 m. The layers are composed mainly of gray clayey silt showing low values of bearing capacity. The clayey silt possibly contains rock flour and shows little or no plasticity. It is highly compressible and susceptible to piping by seeping water forces. Below 5 m or so very dense silty sand with trace gravel exists. The bearing capacity values are quite high.

Fig. 2 : The deposit shows fluctuating *N* and *ABC* values indicating medium to very high density. In the upper layers the silty sands contain some clay sized particles but the lower layers are essentially sands, non-plastic and very dense.

Overall speaking upto the depth investigated for normal engineering constructions, the sub soils possess medium to high bearing capacity in the North Bengal.

Further details will be given in Part-III + of the paper.

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